

Postcards from the edge: SARS-CoV-2 pandemic narratives in fiction film and documentaries

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Summary

Public perception about infectious diseases, science, and public health policies can be affected by exposure to related works of art, including film, and may modify one's actions during a pandemic. An increasing number of fiction films and documentaries are inspired from the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic. Major narratives include: the inadequate early response of governments and international organizations, the heroic actions of healthcare practitioners, the social effect of lockdown (both as a spirit-raising inducer of togetherness and as a disproportionately harsh burden on minorities and underprivileged), the individual effect of lockdown on families, and the historical significance of certain major pandemic events. But these works of art also depict individual stories, of celebration and victory or mourning, favored by their immediacy, their

chronological closeness to the events. In depicting these pandemic aspects, often subjectively, fiction films and documentaries can evolve into historical documents but also influence health literacy of future generations.

Key words

SARS-CoV-2; COVID-19; pandemic; cinema; arts; documentary

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Introduction

Every infectious disease outbreak, let alone a pandemic of the magnitude and duration of the SARS-CoV-2 one, is also a social phenomenon, its course partly shaped by the public's behavior: the latter's perception of risk, its adherence to mitigating public health measures, its ability to understand scientific messaging and its willingness to embrace scientific breakthroughs – all that comprise health literacy. Individual infectious disease literacy is constructed by varying influences and preexisting perceptions, which can be shaped by representations of outbreaks, epidemics, and pandemics in film and television,^{1,2} media that are accessible and attention-grabbing.

Moreover, film and television can serve in historical documentation of an epidemic/ pandemic, either through documentaries, or through fiction. The present article aims to summarize how the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic has been represented on screen, either in documentary or fiction form.

Search strategy and selection criteria

Apart from personal viewing experience, the author searched the Internet Movie Database, a comprehensive database of film and television productions, using

keywords "covid-19" and "coronavirus". The titles included in the Wikipedia lists of "Television shows about the COVID-19 pandemic" and "Films about the COVID-19 pandemic" were also evaluated: the distribution of some of the included works precluded their availability for viewing, while some of the listed works have only peripheral relevance to the pandemic and were thus omitted.

Results

Fiction

"*Help*", written by Jack Thorne and directed by Marc Munden for Channel 4, is arguably the most significant fiction work related to the current pandemic: Jody Comer's character starts working as an inexperienced nurse in a care home just before the pandemic. She has barely managed to acquaint herself with her duties and residents, when the first SARS-CoV-2 wave sweeps the UK. The care home director struggles to obtain personal protective equipment for his personnel (Comer's character uses garbage bags instead of gowns), but is also obliged to accommodate further residents as hospitals seek space for COVID-19 patients. The virus unavoidably enters the care home and causes an outbreak involving both staff and residents. Comer's character ends up in a

protracted shift alone, desperately trying to help an ailing patient with the assistance of Stephen Graham's character, an early Alzheimer's sufferer. This is a claustrophobic scene, heartrendingly acted by Comer, that outlines the helplessness of care home personnel and residents in the early pandemic days, during which the mortality burden in such institutions was disproportionate. In *"Help"*, despair leads to escapism, before a final laconic attack on the public health policies of the British government in the first pandemic phase.

"Beat the Devil", written and directed by celebrated playwright David Hare is a screen adaptation of Hare's theater monologue detailing his own experience with COVID-19 and subsequent long-COVID symptoms. Screened by Showtime in the US and Sky Arts in UK, it stars, as on stage, Ralph Fiennes in an acting tour de force. The first part details the evolution of symptoms, his illness, his "air hunger", his dysgeusia, his fears, his residual debilitation. But the second part erupts: Fiennes' voice incorporates the torture and anger of the souls of the departed. "I have survivor's rage" he states, not only for the repetitive inadequate state response but also for the absence of sincere public briefing: "Have they really not yet learned that the most soothing possible bandage for the wounds inflicted by grief is the truth?"

Of an entirely different tone and scope, *"Chinese Doctors"* directed by the experienced Andrew Lau and released in Chinese cinemas in the summer of 2021, focuses on the experiences of healthcare workers of a Wuhan hospital during the early SARS-CoV-2 outbreak and subsequent lockdown. The tone is heroic and its scenes unashamedly sentimental. A medical director (suffering from early amyotrophic lateral sclerosis) rallies his troops (doctors, nurses, the cleaning staff), admits everyone in need of medical assistance, and struggles to do the best for his patients ("developments in medicine are built on failures", one character states, facing the increased mortality rates). Meanwhile, healthcare practitioners from other Chinese cities arrive to join the battle, hospitals are built from scratch where six-year old girls volunteer and spirit-raising happenings and choreographies are the norm, the utility of Chinese medicine is hinted at more than once, the superior Chinese ethics are explicitly outlined ("other countries don't intubate patients over 70, we do, we care"), the film soundtrack is loud and celebratory and flags are constantly waved. The film does include interesting scientific and social details though: the utility of early intubation is a constant subject of debate between senior medical specialists, the ECMO (Extracorporeal Membrane Oxygenation) mechanism is analyzed, the dilemma of performing a cesarean section on a severely infected

pregnant woman serves as a major subplot, and the importance of non-healthcare essential workers is outlined through the story of the father-to-be, a delivery man. Despite these interesting details though, and the deserved praise for Wuhan healthcare personnel, the film chooses to end in the same flag waving tone, stating that "they fought a battle of pandemic prevention". This was not exactly their battle, as depicted in some of the documentaries subsequently discussed.

Dany Boon's *"8 Rue de l'Humanité"* (known in English audiences as *"Stuck Together"*), shown in Netflix, focuses on the residents of a Parisian apartment complex during the first pandemic lockdown. The initial disagreements of the different inhabitants are eventually replaced by a sense of camaraderie: The hypochondriac Boon's character; the racist rich pandemic denier (who also has a stock of hydroxychloroquine); the mad scientist seeking guinea pigs for his SARS-CoV-2 vaccine experiments; the young singer who becomes famous by uploading her "Pandemie" song on the internet (it will unbearably stick on your mind too...). Humor is elicited by zoom accidents and the ground-floor pub's alcohol residue turning into a thriving antiseptic business. "It took a pandemic to get to know each other" is the central message, delivered in the typical for Boon anodyne comedic style. Its most significant subplot though includes the mysterious new resident of northern African descent that goes out early at night, every night, and is the subject of general distrust: she turns out to be an emergency medicine specialist who works at nights and chose to rent a room separately from her family in order to avoid the risk of bringing the virus home.

"All U Need is Love" could be considered the Hong Kong equivalent to Boon's film, although its social commentary is sacrificed to cheap laughs. Directed by Vincent Kok and produced in order to support film industry workers affected by the pandemic, its characters are forced to quarantine for two weeks in a hotel, with new relationships and a better understanding growing, even between crooks.

"The Bubble", directed for Netflix by Judd Apatow is an unfunny comedy focusing on a film crew isolated in a comfortable hotel (echoing actual events during the production of a forthcoming Jurassic park sequel). These are privileged individuals that gain limited audience sympathy, and the only remarkable scene is the one of an influenza mini-outbreak: everyone is relieved to hear that they have not contracted SARS-CoV-2, but instead "the good virus".

The individual effect of lockdown on a family is discussed in *"Together"*, written by Dennis Kelly and directed by Stephen Daldry, debuting in BBC2 but re-

leased theatrically in the US. James McAvoy and Sharon Horgan are masterful as the ex-couple deciding to spend the first lockdown together for the sake of their child. They continuously break the fourth wall, discussing with the audience the origins of their relationship, their backgrounds and the social effect of the pandemic as it evolves outside their apartment. Its tight narration dissects a relationship and failed marriage as adequately as the social unrest caused by the pandemic. *"Together"* would be a significant achievement even if it was composed only by its last frame (two kids jumping in their trampolines, both alone in their yards, divided by a tall fence), a symbol of childhood moments lost to the pandemic.

Another couple in distress is at the epicenter of *"Locked Down"*, written by Steven Knight and directed by Doug Liman, released by HBO Max. Anne Hathaway and Chiwetel Ejiofor star as the London-based couple who gradually sink in indifference (as seen in their communications with friends and colleagues) and depression, already being at distance. They decide to steal a diamond exhibited at Harrods, in an effort to invigorate their lives and relationship. There are few things to learn about the pandemic here, and few cinematic things to cherish too.

"The Falls", by respected Taiwanese director Chung Mong-hong, is an award-winning feature examining the hardships of a mother and a daughter during the pandemic, the problems starting with the daughter's self-isolation as a case contact, and evolving during the following months. Although the constant mask wearing reminds us that the pandemic further imposes a burden on their hardships, the pandemic remains a peripheral frame to an otherwise excellent drama.

The Swedish drama *"Orca"*, directed by Josephine Bornebusch, films various characters forced to isolate on their own, as they interact and deal with complex relationships through telecommunication. Again, the pandemic is the cause, but the rest of the drama deals with irrelevant situations.

The limited television series *"Love in the Time of Corona"*, created by Joanna Johnson for Freeform, focusing on the complications of the protagonists' love life during the first lockdown, deserves a mention, partly for its imaginative title reference to Gabriel Garcia Marquez, and partly for being one of the first fiction works inspired from the pandemic to emerge.

"Coastal Elites", written by Paul Rudnick and directed by Jay Roach, for HBO is comprised of five monologues, the latter of which belongs to a volunteer nurse in New York City's first wave, emotionally devastated by the chaos around her, particularly from the loss of a specific patient she bonded with.

"Songbird", written by Simon Boyes and Adam Mason and directed by the latter, released by STX Films, is pandemic exploitation. It takes place in 2023 Los Angeles, in lockdown week 312, the pandemic still going on with the 2023 SARS-CoV-2 variant, with immunity considered a curse!, and the infected imprisoned in concentration camps. A young adult love story evolves in this dystopia, but the film's distance from certain disinformation pandemic narratives is dangerously narrow.

"Safer at Home", directed by Will Wernick and distributed by Vertical Entertainment, also exploits the pandemic, but is at least an engaging thriller narrated entirely through a video chat, its, irrelevant to the plot, introduction and ending places action in August 2022, when a more deadly strain of SARS-CoV-2 has caused more than 31 million deaths in the US and 253 million deaths worldwide, while powerful countries are falling apart, including the UK.

The pandemic as a parody

Sacha Baron Cohen's *"Borat Subsequent Moviefilm"* is an unashamedly blasphemous sequel to the original Borat film, finding once again his character, a journalist from Kazakhstan, traveling in America and insulting practically everything. This is the pandemic US though, and Borat is particularly interested in QAnon believers. The animosity between Donald Trump and Anthony Fauci is the inspiration of a Kazakhstani carnival happening, but the single most important scene is the notorious setup with Rudy Giuliani, cited on camera as believing that SARS-CoV-2 was deliberately released by the Chinese. The origins of the virus though according to Borat, are more sinister and complex: Borat is the vector through which the virus was deliberately released from Kazakhstan (Wuhan being an early stopover in this journey).

"Death to 2020" and its sequel *"Death to 2021"* are satire specials created for Netflix by Charlie Brooker. Both are inhabited by fictional characters who discuss the major 2020 and 2021 events, especially the US politics. But particularly for 2020, the pandemic is woven tightly with US politics: *"It felt like the government wasn't taking the coronavirus seriously. Maybe because there were still folks out there comparing it to the flu, which is like comparing Uruguay to a banana. And one of those folks was the President"*. One has to mention Christine Milioti's exquisitely developed role as a soccer mom who transforms from an early Fauci admirer to a Nazi sympathizer and QAnon radical (and, in the sequel, in a Capitol invader).

The limited television series *"The Bite"* created by Robert and Michelle King, has a deadly new SARS-CoV-2 strain emerging, transmitted through biting

and turning the infected into zombies. A lot of black humor and blood in its six episodes, and eventually the treatment IS a combination of bleach and sunshine!

The documentaries

"In the Same Breath" is directed by Nanfu Wang for HBO Documentary Films and was shortlisted, but not eventually nominated, for the Documentary Feature category for the 94th Academy Awards. Wang had the unfortunate privilege of living the first pandemic waves from the inside both in China AND the US. Built through the stories of everyday people and dedicated to Chen Qiushi, the Chinese activist journalist who was detained and missing for almost a year and a half, it outlines all the inadequacies of both countries' initial response, their governments downplaying the viral threat: Testimonies of people turned away from hospital admission in Wuhan, the hesitancy in proclaiming the obvious (person-to-person transmission) by Chinese officials, but also Anthony Fauci reassuringly citing in February 17, 2020 that "it is the flu we should worry about". The personal protective equipment shortage, the healthcare workers' post-traumatic stress disorders, and the sheer death toll of the pandemic are solemnly, and thus most effectively, narrated. This is a story of the people's pandemic, so different to the one narrated by governments.

"The First Wave" is directed by Mathew Heineman (a documentarist with an excellent resume on combat zones' depictions) for the National Geographic Documentary Films and was also shortlisted but not nominated for the Documentary Feature category for the 94th Academy Awards. Its heroes are healthcare workers during the first New York City pandemic wave. "We were taught patterns of disease recognition but right now there is no clear pattern"; "you have no weapons"; "everyday we look death right in its eye, the scary thing is that death looks right back to us"; pure urgency, moments of silence when a battle for a patient's life is lost, physical and mental exhaustion of healthcare personnel along with their own fears of getting infected; but also birthdays celebrated through zoom meetings, an Albert Camus quote on a webinar slide, the Beatles' "Here Comes the Sun" as the triumphant tune every time a successful extubation goes on. What makes *"The First Wave"* an essential pandemic testimony is its focus on the minorities: its patients, doctors and nurses belong to minorities (the "I Can't Breathe" disarray adding to the pandemic one). The 35 year old overweight diabetic essential worker that survives COVID-19 and is reunited over the phone with his family after extubation IS the world's hope and victory.

"76 Days" is the Chinese equivalent to *"The First Wave"*. Directed by Hao Wu, Weixi Chen and an anonymous individual for MTV Documentaries, it was shortlisted for the Documentary Feature category of the 93th Academy Awards last year, but did not secure a nomination. In a flag-waving mode similar to *"Chinese Doctors"*, its healthcare personnel are all anonymous and never tired (apart from a single momentary initial grief). The urgency is present here too, but the memorable moments are scarce (a bracelet to be removed from a swollen hand posthumously, as an inheritance for the relatives) or politically charged (an old man attempting to exit from the hospital, reprimanded by his son for not being a worthy party member).

"Coronation", directed by Ai Weiwei, is guerrilla film making, its footage filmed covertly by volunteers and personnel hired by Wei. Scenes from Wuhan, era March 2020 are abundant (of particular interest are the ones offering a glimpse of the inside of specially built hospitals) but unfocused, often shifting its interest to the general political situation in China.

David France directed *"How to Survive a Pandemic"* for HBO,³ his credentials including 2012's Academy Award-nominated *"How to Survive a Plague"* about the early HIV days. Its first part looks like an insightful recapitulation of the race to produce a vaccine, the Operation Warp Speed, and the political interference ("please next pandemic virus, do not come on an election year"), aided by interviews with numerous key pandemic figures: *Science* journalist Jon Cohen serves as our host, and Peter Marks, Adrian Hill, Dan Barouch, Kizzmekia Corbett, Paul Offit, Seth Berkley, Moncef Siaoui, General Perna, and Anthony Fauci all address the camera. Key moments include the champagne opening in Pfizer headquarters in early November 2020, with a toast "to breakthroughs"; Marks' coordination of the FDA regulation process from his basement, and Offit's emotional voting moment during FDA's approval meeting. The second part is, through Cohen's questions, more interventional. It addresses the controversies about the AstraZeneca trials, vaccine roll-out shortcomings and the shortages of the presidential transition period, vaccine hesitancy and particularly its burden on minorities (and the important role of religious community leaders in reversing it), and global vaccine inequity. Characteristic moments include Cohen's meeting with Serum Institute of India's CEO: Cohen inquires about the Institute's broken promises to COVAX about vaccine delivery. The latter, Adar Poonawalla, responds "without ME, essentially COVAX would fail". The South African burden of disease due to the Beta variant (for which the AstraZeneca vaccine was considered inactive) and the efforts to ensure certain Johnson & Johnson vaccine

doses for the healthcare personnel is narrated by Glenda Gray of the South African Medical Research Council. Cohen's final meeting is with Dr. Tedros Ghebreyesus, addressing once more the inequities.

"54 Days" is a BBC2 two-part program also focusing on initial response, both in China and the US. The first part, "China and the pandemic" is of significant value as, through its clinical narration, constructs a story of Chinese authorities' negligence and international authorities' hesitance or arrogance, ones that made the pandemic unavoidable. Numerous key statesmen are interviewed, Lawrence Gostin discussing the International Health Regulations, Ian Lipkin describing a telephone call with Chinese CDC's George Gao on December 31, 2019, Peter Daszak remembering contacting ProMed's Marjorie Pollack on the same day, "knowing from a good source that it is transmissible from person-to-person and is SARS-like" and offering help to Gao but getting a blank answer ("Happy New Year!"), Edward Holmes remembering old photos/ documents from wet markets and the first announcement of the viral genome, Maria van Kerkhove admitting that she considered person-to-person transmission obvious since day one (but accepting that the Chinese state's delays in passing adequate information to WHO is a norm, happening with most countries in similar situations). The documentary also focuses on the Chinese surveillance system failure and on the restrictions imposed by the state and party on distribution of scientific information, and also hosts internal data obtained by Associated Press from WHO meetings and Chinese directives (with the potential of a pandemic acknowledged as early as January 14, 2020). An essential, enlightening tool for reconstructing the initial history of the pandemic.

"Totally Under Control" comes from the prolific Alex Gibney, co-directed with Ophelia Harutyunyan and Suzanne Hillinger, for Neon. In a combat and loud ("look how complicated by the pandemic our shoot was!") mode, it attacks the Trump Administration for its inadequate response to the pandemic. Some of the infuriating inconsistencies can be attributed to bureaucratic short-circuits (the initially approved non-functional diagnostic tests leading to the lost month of testing), but mostly it is the Administration that is to blame: the misinformation, the downplaying of the viral severity, the competition between federal government and states in personal protection equipment bidding, the subsequent sidelining of Nancy Messonnier and Rick Bright, the hydroxychloroquine saga. An excellent point is made about South Korea's response in contrast to the US (the test-trace-isolate approach, so exquisitely deployed in the Shincheonji Church of Jesus outbreak, the drive through testing,

the personal protective equipment in situ production). There is room for exaggeration though when one is loud: January 2020 prophetic quotes are supported by late February 2020 emails, and the expertise of some of the experts recruited can be considered debatable. Similarly, the hydroxychloroquine story is largely based on the Vladimir Zelenko involvement (understandably since Zelenko is interviewed), omitting the Marseilles effect (Trump IS shown referencing the relevant study).

"Fauci" is a biographical documentary directed by John Hoffman and Janet Tobias for National Geographic Documentary Films, distributed by Magnolia Pictures. Essentially an hagiography, it nevertheless outlines the many significant parallels between the first years of the HIV pandemic and the current one. It further depicts the vast societal division created (or enhanced) during this pandemic, Fauci being both a devil for some, and a rock star for others (thus, unavoidably, Bono comments too).

Hannah Olson's "The Last Cruise", for HBO, recreates the Diamond Princess outbreak through traveler and ship personnel testimonies. Two of the most striking scenes include the packed personnel dormitories (which readily explain the rapid viral transmission between staff) and a flight back, masks retrospectively scarily inadequately used, anxious or sick and tired faces behind them.

The television medical regulars

Unavoidably, regular television series of medical interest ("The Good Doctor", "New Amsterdam", "Chicago Med") focused on the pandemic when their new seasons started in the Fall of 2020, although few managed to offer any significant insights. "Grey's Anatomy" can be considered an exception, not only because its central character was infected from SARS-CoV-2 and intubated during the 17th season, but also because it addressed important parameters, as care home outbreaks and patients who are pandemic deniers in certain of its episodes. A further analysis has been published recently.⁴

Conclusion

Films and documentaries serve various purposes in both normal life and in times of urgency. The aforementioned works of art underline specific narratives that are useful in understanding how the public viewed the pandemic and what public health response aspects need clarification (or glorification). A first narrative, particularly by the major documentaries presented above, focuses on the inadequate initial

response of governments, organizations, and even the scientific community, and is outlined as a subject that should be further explored. The second major narrative is the one of the healthcare workers' heroic response during extremely strained conditions, a response that sometimes is misused in order to mask state inadequacies. The third obvious narrative is the social effect of the pandemic, depicted either as a benign fable of togetherness, or as the actual harsh pandemic toll in minorities and care homes. This social effect is often used as a special effect though, the pandemic being a peripheral environment minimally influencing what is evolving on screen. A fourth narrative includes the individual, family toll of the pandemic and particularly lockdowns: strained relationships and isolation are the predominant themes of this narratives, although the extreme effects on domestic violence and mental health disorientation have been vaguely depicted until now. Finally, the fifth significant narrative is the historical approach, the facts, the events to be remembered, devoid of critique or subjective evaluation.

At the time of writing, the pandemic is into its third year, and pandemic fatigue may also influence the effect of these feature films and documentaries on the public. One could thus attribute the absence of eventual Academy Award nomination for the two short-listed documentaries (*In the Same Breath* and *The First Wave*) as an index of pandemic fatigue: the public, including the Academy voters, wants to put such memories behind.

Eventually the pandemic can be viewed as a series of individual stories, both tragic and inspiring. Fiction and documentaries may attempt to be strictly objective or overtly sentimental. Both approaches leave behind a snapshot of a turbulent era. Undoubtedly, the following years will offer more and more cinematic recreations of this era and will be able to approach more philosophically these narratives. These first ones though have the immediacy of now, and are thus, signs of their own times.

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Nothing to declare.

Περίληψη

Αναφορές από την Τέχνη: αφηγήσεις πανδημίας SARS-CoV-2 σε ταινίες μυθοπλασίας και ντοκιμαντέρ

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Η αντίληψη του κοινού για τις μολυσματικές ασθένειες, την επιστήμη και τις πολιτικές δημόσιας υγείας μπορεί να επηρεαστεί από την τέχνη, συμπεριλαμβανομένου του κινηματογράφου, με αποτέλεσμα να τροποποιήσει την αντίδρασή του κατά τη διάρκεια μιας πανδημίας. Ένας αυξανόμενος αριθμός ταινιών μυθοπλασίας και ντοκιμαντέρ εμπνέεται από την πανδημία SARS-CoV-2. Τα κύρια αφηγήματα περιλαμβάνουν: την ανεπαρκή έγκαιρη ανταπόκριση των κυβερνήσεων και των διεθνών οργανισμών, τις ηρωικές ενέργειες των επαγγελματιών υγείας, το κοινωνικό αποτέλεσμα του "lockdown" (τόσο ως παράγοντας που ενισχύει την κοινωνική ομοψυχία, όσο και ως δυσανάλογα σκληρό βάρος για τις μειονότητες και τους μη προνομιούχους), την επίδραση του "lockdown" στις οικογένειες και την ιστορική σημασία ορισμένων σημειώντων γεγονότων της πανδημίας. Αλλά αυτά τα έργα τέχνης απεικονίζουν και μεμονωμένες ιστορίες, γιορτής και νίκης ή πένθους, που ευνοούνται από την αμεσότητά τους, καθώς και τη χρονολογική τους εγγύτητα με τα γεγονότα. Κατά την απεικόνιση αυτών των πτυχών της πανδημίας, συχνά υποκειμενική, οι ταινίες μυθοπλασίας και τα ντοκιμαντέρ μπορούν να εξελιχθούν σε ιστορικά ντοκουμέντα, αλλά και να επηρεάσουν τη γνώση και την αντίληψη περί Υγείας των μελλοντικών γενεών.

Λέξεις κλειδιά

SARS-CoV-2, COVID-19, πανδημία, κινηματογράφος, τέχνες, ντοκιμαντέρ

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